

A Secondary Analysis of the NSQIP Database to Reduce Adverse Postoperative Respiratory Occurrences

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Background

- Adverse Postoperative Respiratory Occurrences (APROs) occur in as many as 49% of patients undergoing surgery.
- APROs occur in 15-40% of patients after major thoracic surgery.
- APROs are the primary cause of mortality and morbidity after lung resections, with a mortality rate of 20-50%.
- APROs contribute to poor long-term outcomes, increase the length of stay and increase healthcare costs.

Purpose

The purpose of this scholarly Doctor of Nursing Science project was to conduct a secondary data analysis using the National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) database to identify predictors that would lead to APROs. These include pneumonia, unplanned intubation, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation (>48 hours).

Setting

Project Topic Identified From:

- 314 bed acute care facility in San Bernardino County.
- Provides both inpatient and outpatient surgical procedures, including thoracic cases.

Data Analyzed From:

- ACS NSQIP database.
- Compiled from 865 sites in the United States.

Methods

- Secondary data analysis of NSQIP data.
- Utilized Iowa Model Framework.
- Inclusion criteria: Adult patients (≥ 18 years), thoracic surgery (closed or open approach), and non-emergent. Included cases were based on 206 CPT codes for thoracic surgery.
- Exclusion criteria: Pediatric patients (<18 years old), cardiac surgery, and urgent or emergent procedures.
- Each APRO case was matched 1:1 with a control case (non-APRO) based on CPT code and age (+/- 5 years).

Results & Data Analysis

- ACS NSQIP contains 260 HIPAA-compliant variables on 983,851 cases from 865 sites in 2021.
- 6331 cases were identified.
- Descriptive and conditional logistic regression was performed for each APRO.
- Five variables were analyzed for each APRO; gender, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine, albumin, and hematocrit.

Pulmonary Embolism

- $n = 35$
- 0.55% of thoracic cases
- 4.85% of all APROs

Pneumonia

- $n = 382$
- 6.03% of thoracic cases
- 52.91% of all APROs

Unplanned Intubation

- $n = 151$
- 2.39% of thoracic case
- 20.91% of all APROs

Failure to Wean

- $n = 154$
- 2.43% of thoracic cases
- 21.33% of all APROs

Statistically Significant Predictors of APROs

APRO	Predictors	B	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval Limit
Pulmonary Embolism	Albumin	- 1.36	.25	.08 - .82
	Hematocrit	.22	1.25	1.05 - 1.48
Pneumonia	Albumin	- .58	.56	.42 - .74
Unplanned Intubations	Sex	.64	1.89	1.08 - 3.32
	Creatinine	.45	1.57	1.05 - 2.35
	Albumin	- .80	.45	.27 - .76
	Hematocrit	- .06	.95	.90 - 1.00
Failure to Wean	Albumin	- .53	.59	.37 - .93
	Hematocrit	- .08	.92	.87 - .98

Discussion

- Correlation between preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, and sex in the development of APROs following thoracic surgery.
- Preoperative hypoalbuminemia was significantly associated with all 4 APROs.
- Preoperative hematocrit was significantly associated with 3 out of the 4 APROs.

Limitations

Project Limitations

- Data analyzed was restricted to one year.
- Multiple surgeries cancelled in 2021 due to SARS-COVID-19 pandemic.

NSQIP Limitations

- Certain variables, such as frailty and serum lactate levels, are not included.
- Selection bias, as participation was voluntary.
- APROs are not tracked after 30 days.
- Specially trained clinical reviewer required to collect data.
- Disproportionate amount of teaching hospitals.

Recommendations

- Development of a preoperative checklist for patients undergoing thoracic surgery to assess risk for developing an APRO.
 - With an emphasis on preoperative albumin levels.
- Check albumin, creatinine, and hematocrit levels on patients prior to thoracic surgery.
- Optimize patient's laboratory values prior to surgery to attain a serum albumin > 3.5g/dL, hematocrit > 35%, and creatinine < 1.2mg/dL.
- Expand data collection to include multiple years for which NSQIP data is observed.
- Limit the amount of APROs studied to one.

Conclusion

- APROs are a significant complication in patients undergoing thoracic surgery.
- Assess lab values, specifically albumin, creatinine, and hematocrit, in individuals undergoing thoracic surgery to evaluate risk for developing an APRO.
- Preoperative albumin and hematocrit levels play a vital role in the development of APROs.

References

The American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program and the hospitals participating in the ACS NSQIP are the source of the data used herein; they have not verified and are not responsible for the statistical validity of the data analysis or the conclusions derived by the authors.